

EVALUATION OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF *SHRIKHAND* PREPARED FROM BEETROOT POWDER.

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(MS Received: 23.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:30.12.2023)

MS 3121

(RESEARCH PAPER IN DAIRY SCIENCE,)

Abstract

Present study was carried for assessment of *Shrikhand* prepared by supplementation of beetroot powder. The *Shrikhand* was made from buffalo milk by supplementing with different levels of beetroot powder with different treatment and the chemical composition was carried out. In present study, beetroot powder was used as additive for preparation of *Shrikhand*. The beetroot powder was added in different treatment T_0 , T_1 , T_2 , T_3 and T_4 with different levels of 0%, 3%, 5%, 7% and 9% in respectively. The physio-chemical properties of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* the range of protein content for *Shrikhand* samples was 9.53 to 13.10 per cent and the range of fat was found to be 9.05 to 8.85 per cent. The acidity for *Shrikhand* samples was 1.04 to 1.35 for treatment T_0 to T_4 and pH range for *Shrikhand* was 5.10 to 4.84 respectively. The ranges of sucrose and lactose content was 40.00 to 47.38 and 3.50 to 4.15 per cent respectively. The ranges of total solid, SNF and moisture content was found to be 63.12 to 74.83, 54.07 to 65.98 and 22.95 to 20.89 respectively. From the current study it was observed that the addition of beetroot powder levels raised the protein, acidity, sucrose, lactose, total solid, SNF and decreased the fat, pH and moisture percentage.

Keys Words: - Beetroot, *Shrikhand*, Fat, Protein, Acidity, pH, sucrose, lactose, TS and SNF, moisture.

Introduction

A semisolid, soft, slightly sweet, slightly bitter dairy product is called *Shrikhand*. During festivals and ceremonial events, *Shrikhand* is served as a particular delicacy. It has been suggested that consuming *Shrikhand* can help improve a variety of illnesses, including diarrhoeas, acidity and digestive (Patel and Schequen, 1999).

Popular desert *Shrikhand* is served as a delectable addition to religious ceremonies in the state of Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka and some regions of South India (Aneja et al., 2002)

The world most popular dairy products are fermented due to their excellent nutritional and medicinal value. Fermentation is also a means of preserving nutrients in milk and various fermentation products are developed. *Shrikhand* is a semi solid, sweetish-sour fermented milk product prepared from *dahi*, whey is drained off from *dahi* to yield *Chakka*. *Chakka* to form a soft homogenous mass it is mixed with sugar, colour and flavour that resembles sweetened quarg of Germany. Charoli, cardamom, nutmeg, saffron and almond are added to improve the taste and nutritional quality.

Beetroot (*Beta vulgaris rubra*) is crop belonging to the family Chenopodiaceae having, important raw material of plant origin with proven positive effects on the human body and bright crimson colour. It is also useful as medicine properties, juice and also known by several names such as spinach beet, chard, beet, sea beet, garden beet, white beet and Chukander (in Hindi). They can also be eaten as raw, boiled, steamed and roasted. Red beetroot is a rich source of minerals (manganese, sodium, potassium, magnesium, iron, copper). Beetroot contains a lot of antioxidants, vitamins (A, C, B), fiber and natural dyes. Red beetroot is also rich in phenol compounds, which have antioxidant properties. These colorful root vegetables help to protect against heart disease and certain cancers (colon cancer) (Kavalcova et al., 2015). Beetroot is a source of calcium, iron, potassium and magnesium. It's also contains biologically active plant nutrient called phytonutrients. These phytonutrients may play role in lowering a person's risk of chronic diseases.

Beets have long been known for its amazing health benefits for almost every part of the body. Start adding beets to your juicing diet

to enjoy all its heavenly goodness. Beet roots is also useful for Anemia, Blood pressure, Cancer, Gastric ulcer, Kidney ailments, Skin disorders, Increases sex drive, Lowers cholesterol and etc. Yashwant Kumar 2015.

Material & Methods

The current research work was completed in the research facility of Department of Dairy Science & Technology established in the Vivekanand Arts, Sardar Dalipsingh Commerce & Science College, Aurangabad

Buffalo milk, procured from the local market, was standardized to 9.0 per cent Solid Not Fat (SNF) and 6.0 per cent fat for preparation of *Chakka*. Beetroot powder, manufacture by bhoom Industry LTD, was used as value added ingredient for preparation of *Shrikhand*.

Preparation of *Shrikhand* through addition of Beetroot powder:

The process for preparation of *Shrikhand* through addition of beetroot powder is illustrated in flow chart given Fig No 1.

Treatment details:-

The preliminary trial were conducted with five different levels of beetroot powder was added in different treatment T_0 , T_1 , T_2 , T_3 and T_4 with different levels of 0%, 3%, 5%, 7% and 9% in respectively.

Physico-chemical Analysis of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

The samples of *Shrikhand* prepared with five different levels of beetroot powder was added in different treatment T_0 , T_1 , T_2 , T_3 and T_4 with different levels of 0%, 3%, 5%, 7% and 9% in respectively for analysis of Physico-chemical i.e acidity, protein, fat, pH, fat, sucrose, lactose, Total solid, Solid Not Fat and moisture,

Result and Discussion**Acidity of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand***

Titration acidity of a dairy product system is indicative of the total acid concentration present in product and is estimated by titration method. The acidity score of *Shrikhand* by using beetroot powder is presented in table no 1.

Treatments	T_0	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4
	1.04	1.12	1.22	1.31	1.35

Table No 1. Acidity of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

The acidity score of *Shrikhand* was found in the range 1.04 and 1.35. The mean score for the acidity were 1.04, 1.12, 1.22, 1.31 & 1.35 for *Shrikhand* prepared under treatments T_0 , T_1 , T_2 , T_3 & T_4 respectively. It is observed from the data that the average value of *Shrikhand* went on increasing due to the addition of beetroot powder. It is observe

from the table that the highest acidity score was 1.35 in T_4 and the lowest acidity score was 1.04 in T_0 . All the treatment were significantly different from each other. From these research study it is found that if acidity of any fermented product increased similarly pH of product decreased. Nigam et al (2009) observed that addition of

different level of papaya pulp significantly affect the acidity of *Shrikhand*, he conducted the study using 0,20,40,60 percent papaya

pulp on the basis of chakka. He found that as the levels of papaya pulp increase the acidity of *Shrikhand* also increased.

Fig ;-1.Manufacture of *Shrikhand* (flow chart)

Protein Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

Protein is one of the essential amino acid contain in any dairy product in terms of its healthy constitution. Protein has different role in human bodies and helps to repairs, build human body tissue. The protein percent in beetroot powder has 1.68 gm per 100 gms of beetroot

powder. The protein percentage for prepared product was estimated by the Kjeldhal's method. The details of protein score of different *Shrikhand* treatments, prepared during present study by using different levels of beetroot powder is given in table 2.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	9.53	10.39	11.29	12.51	13.10

Table No 2. Protein of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

The score for protein of various *Shrikhand* treatments varied from 9.53 to 13.10. The mean values of score for protein of *Shrikhand* prepared under treatments T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ were 9.53, 10.39, 11.29, 12.51 and 13.10 respectively. It is observed from the data that the average value of *Shrikhand* goes on increasing due to the addition of beetroot powder. It is observe from the table that the highest protein score was 13.10 in T₄ and the lowest score of protein was 9.53 in T₀. All the treatment were significantly different from each other.

From the current research study it is observed that protein content of shrikhnd increases from T₀ to T₄. With the increasing level of beetroot powder all the treatment are significantly different from each other. Devid (2015) also observed the same result in *Shrikhand* prepared using basil extract i.e protein increase with increase of basil extract 1%, 2%, 3% and 4% respectively.

pH Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

The pH of any dairy product decides basic or acidic nature of the product. The pH of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* was assessed by digital pH meter at room temperature. The current typical score is

accounted for beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* is given in table 3.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	5.10	5.00	4.95	4.91	4.84

Table No 3. pH of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

The table 3 indicate that, the average score of pH contents under different treatment of different levels of beetroot powder were declined and agreement with the inversely proportion of acidity and pH. The score for pH content were 5.10,5.00,4.95,4.91 and 4.84 for the treatments T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. The greatest pH was observed in control T₀ (5.10) and the lowest pH in T₄ (4.84) these was due to increases in the acidity of *Shrikhand* as compared to decreased

in the pH content due to addition of beetroot powder . In current investigation all the treatments were significantly different from each other.

4. Fat Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

The observation regarding the fat content in *Shrikhand* by using beetroot powder of different treatment is represented in table 4.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	9.05	9.04	8.96	8.90	8.85

Table No 4. Fat of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

From the table it is observed that the fat content in product range in 9.05 to 8.85. The largest fat content was experiential for T₀ 9.05 (0% of beetroot powder) and the lowest fat per cent was found in T₄ 8.85 (9% of beetroot powder) The observation from the table clearly showed that as the increased in beetroot powder there is decreased in fat percent of the product. The means average score for fat content was 9.05, 9.04, 8.96, 8.90 and 8.85 at different treatment T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. Gavan et al (2010) reported that addition of different level of custard apple pulp significantly affect the fat of

Shrikhand. He found that using 0,1,2,3,4 and 5 per cent custard apple pulp on the basis of chakka, observed that the levels of custard apple pulp increased with decrease the fat of *Shrikhand*, whereas *Shrikhand* made from 5 % (T₅) custard apple obtained the lowest fat per cent.

5. Sucrose Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

The details of sucrose score of different *Shrikhand* treatments, prepared during present study by using different levels of beetroot powder is given in table 5.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	40.00	42.47	44.10	45.75	47.38

Table No 5. Sucrose of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

The Sucrose score of various *Shrikhand* treatments varied from 40.00 to 47.38. The mean values score for sucrose of *Shrikhand* prepared under treatments T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ were 40.00,42.47, 44.10,45.75 and 47.38 respectively. It is seen from the information that the typical worth of *Shrikhand* continued expanding because of the expansion of beetroot powder. It is see from the table that the most elevated sucrose score was 47.38 in T₄ and the least score of sucrose was 40.00 in T₀ . All the treatment were significantly different from

each other. From the current research study it is observed that protein content of shrikhd increases from T₀ to T₄. With the increasing level of beetroot powder all the treatment are significantly different from each other.

6. Lactose Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

The details of lactose score of different *Shrikhand* treatments, prepared during present study by using different levels of beetroot powder is given in table 6.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	3.50	3.89	4.01	4.10	4.15

Table No 6. lactose of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

The score for lactose of various *Shrikhand* treatments varies from 3.50 to 4.15. The mean values of score for lactose of *Shrikhand* prepared under treatments T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ were 3.50,3.89,4.01,4.10 and 4.15 respectively. It is observed from the data that the average value of *Shrikhand* increases due to the addition of beetroot powder. It is observe from the table that the maximum sucrose score was 4.15 in T₄ and the minimum score of lactose was 3.50 in T₀ . All the treatment were significantly different from each other. From the current research study it is observed that lactose

content of *Shrikhand* increases from T₀ to T₄. With the increasing level of beetroot powder all the treatment are significantly different from each other.

7. Total Solid Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

Total solid are that remaining content other than the moisture amount After the removing of moisture then the product is mentions as total solids. The total solids percentage for the preparation of *Shrikhand* from value added beetroot is given in table 7.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	63.12	66.91	69.58	72.57	74.83

Table No 7. Total solids of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

From the table it is clearly observed that average of total solids increases with the increases in different levels of value added beetroot powder in *Shrikhand* at different treatment. The score for total solids of various *Shrikhand* treatments varied from 63.12 to 74.83. The mean values of score for total solids of *Shrikhand* prepared under treatments T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ were 63.12,66.91, 69.58,72.57 and 78.83 respectively. It is observed from the data that the average value of *Shrikhand* increases due to the addition of beetroot powder. It is observe from the table that the maximum total solids score was 74.83 in T₄ and the minimum score of total solids was 74.83 in T₀ . All the

treatment were significantly different from each other. From the current research study it is observed that total solids content of *Shrikhand* increases from T₀ to T₄. With the increasing level of beetroot powder all the treatment are significantly different from each other.

8. Solid Not Fat Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

Solid Not Fat are that remaining content other than the moisture and fat amount. After the removing of moisture and fat that product is mentions as solids not fat. The solid not fat percentage for the

preparation of *Shrikhand* from value added beetroot is given in table 8.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	54.07	57.87	60.62	63.67	65.98

Table No 8. Solid Not Fat of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

From the table it is clearly observed that average of solid not fat increases with the increases in different levels of value added beetroot powder in *Shrikhand* at different treatment. The score for solid not fat of various *Shrikhand* treatments varied from 54.07 to 65.98. The mean values of score for solid not fat of *Shrikhand* prepared under treatments T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ were 54.07, 57.87, 60.62, 63.67 and 65.98 respectively. It is observed from the data that the average value of *Shrikhand* increases due to the addition of beetroot powder. It is observed from the table that the maximum solid not fat score was 65.98 in T₄ and the minimum score of solid not fat was 54.07 in T₀. All the

treatment were significantly different from each other. From the current research study it is observed that solid not fat content of *Shrikhand* increases from T₀ to T₄. With the increasing level of beetroot powder all the treatment are significantly different from each other.

9. Moisture Content of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand*

Moisture denotes the presence of water level in the products. The observed value of moisture of different levels of beetroot powder in different treatment in *Shrikhand* is mentioned in table 9.

Treatments	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
	22.95	22.26	21.80	21.35	20.89

Table No 9. Moisture of beetroot powder added in *Shrikhand* (in per cent)

It showed that the result obtained from table 9, it was revealed that, the percentage of moisture in beetroot powder value added *Shrikhand* was decreased. The percentage of moisture was decreased in T₄ (20.89) as the level of beetroot powder increases (9 % of beetroot powder) added on the basis of chakka. The highest range of moisture was observed in T₀(22.95) at control (0% of beetroot powder). The average means score for moisture of beetroot powder in value added *Shrikhand* under different treatment were listed as 22.95, 22.26, 21.80, 21.35 and 20.89 in the treatment T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. Zine et al (2019) reported that as the levels of addition of inulin powder increased the value of moisture in *Shrikhand* under different treatment decreases. The decreasing moisture content could be due to utilization of water by inulin in gel formation.

Conclusion

Beet has always a vital source of energy enriched with nutrients and fibre. It is biannual and accessible almost throughout the year. Beetroot Powder contains a high concentration of vitamins and nitrates, red beets are a great natural pre-workout & helps in healthy circulation. Beetroot powder also contains biologically active plant nutrients called phytonutrients. These phytonutrients may play a role in lowering a person's risk of chronic diseases. These days, beetroot powder is valued for its complex of medical advantages, particularly in the wellness space, where competitors use it as a pre-workout or pre-exercise. Bearing in mind the facts and health benefits it is decided to use beet root powder for preparation of value added *Shrikhand*. It was observed from the current research that addition of beetroot powder in different levels raised the acidity, protein, sucrose, lactose, Total solids, Solid Not Fat and decreased the pH, fat and moisture.

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